

Pseudoglucagonoma Syndrome/Necrolytic Migratory Erythema in a Patient with Polymedication and Dysbalance between Omega-6/Omega-3 Fatty Acids: A Rare Presentation in a Bulgarian Patient

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Abstract

Pseudoglucagonoma syndrome is an extremely rare condition characterized by necrolytic migratory erythema (NME) in the absence of a glucagon-secreting tumor. NME has been associated with a variety of underlying conditions, including hepatocellular dysfunction, nutritional deficiencies, and etc. We report a rare case of a 69-year-old male diagnosed with pseudoglucagonoma syndrome, represented with histologically confirmed NME without evidence of glucagonoma. The condition was likely triggered by the patient's polymedication for type 2 diabetes mellitus and arterial hypertension. His medical history was notable for metabolic syndrome, hepatic steatosis, and hyperuricemia. Additional dysbalance in the fatty acid levels were noted. Following the discontinuation of the suspected culprit medications, the patient showed rapid clinical improvement. A new classification of NME is proposed, and a multifactorial pathogenesis is suggested in the context of the pseudoglucagonoma syndrome development.

Introduction

The glucagonoma syndrome is a rare condition characterized by a constellation of systemic and dermatological features, which can include excessive secretion of glucagon from a tumor, necrolytic migratory erythema (NME), diabetes mellitus, cheilosis, normochromic and normocytic anemia, weight loss, venous thrombosis, and neuropsychiatric symptoms [1]. At present, the most common symptoms are weight loss (71%), NME (67%), diabetes mellitus (38%),

cheilosis or stomatitis (29%), and diarrhea (29%) (1). Necrolytic migratory erythema, when present alongside diabetes mellitus, is associated with a significantly shorter time to diagnosis - 7 months, compared to an average of up to 4 years when either symptom occurs alone [1].

Pseudoglucagonoma syndrome is an extremely rare condition characterized by the presence of necrolytic migratory erythema without evidence of a glucagon-secreting tumor [2]. The hallmark of glucagonoma

More Information

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syndrome - necrolytic migratory erythema - is likely associated with additional factors or underlying conditions beyond glucagon-secreting tumors [2]. These may include pancreatic insufficiency, pancreatitis, inflammatory bowel disease, hepatocellular dysfunction, gastrointestinal dysfunction, celiac disease, malabsorption disorders, nutritional deficiencies (such as zinc and essential fatty acids), and hypoalbuminemia [2].

We report a rare and unique case of a 69-year-old male diagnosed with pseudoglucagonoma syndrome, presenting with histologically confirmed necrolytic migratory erythema in the absence of a glucagon-secreting tumor, likely as part of a drug-induced reaction following polymedication for type 2 diabetes mellitus and arterial hypertension. Significant medical history included metabolic syndrome, hepatic steatosis, hyperuricemia. Additional dysbalance in the fatty acid levels were noted. After discontinuing the suspected culprit medications, the patient experienced rapid clinical improvement, supporting a possible drug-induced etiology. The need for a revised etiological classification was discussed.

Case Report

A 69-year-old male presented to the dermatology department with a primary complaint of a gradually progressive, polymorphic rash involving the whole body, developing over the past two months. The eruption was accompanied by general malaise and mild pruritus.

The patient medical history is significant for type 2 diabetes mellitus, metabolic syndrome, dyslipidemia, arterial hypertension, ischemic heart disease, chronic right-sided heart failure, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, obstructive sleep apnea, xerosis cutis, acne inversa, hepatic steatosis, hyperuricemia, and polyarthrosis. He is undergoing systemic therapy with acetylsalicylic acid 100 mg once at night, rosuvastatin/ezetimibe 10mg/10mg once in the evening, metoprolol succinate 50 mg once in the morning, furosemide 40 mg once in the morning, spironolactone 25 mg once in the morning, dapagliflozin 10 mg once in the morning, lisinopril/hydrochlorothiazide 10mg/12,5mg twice daily, amlodipine 5mg once in the evening, rilmenidine 1mg once in the morning, budesonide/formoterol fumarate dihydrate 160micrograms/4.5 micrograms - two inhalations twice daily, and intermittent oxygen therapy at 2.5l/min during the day for four hours via BiPAP. Additionally, the patient is receiving semaglutide 14 mg once in the morning, gliclazide 30 mg twice daily, metformin hydrochloride 850 mg once in the evening, thioctic acid 600mg once in the morning, and allopurinol 100 mg once daily.

Routine blood analysis revealed: elevated MCV at 99.2 fL (normal range 82-96 fL), increased RDW-SD at 56.3 fL

(35.0-56.0 fL), elevated MPV at 11.4 fL (6.5-11 fL), elevated PDW at 16.4% (11-15%), decreased lymphocytes at 18.3% (20-40%), reduced HDL at 0.68 mmol/L (1.55-2.0 mmol/L), low LDL at 1.3 mmol/L (1.5-3.0 mmol/L), elevated triglycerides at 2.69 mmol/L (0.08-1.7 mmol/L), elevated glucose levels at 7.65 mmol/L (3.8-6.1 mmol/L), elevated uric acid at 625.0 micromol/L (220-450 micromol/L), elevated ASAT at 77.0 U/L (11-34 U/L), elevated ALAT at 49.0 U/L (0-45 U/L), elevated CRP at 7.8 mg/L (0-5.0 mg/L), elevated CEA at 5.68 ng/mL (less than or equal to 3.0 ng/mL). A quadruple glucose profile was performed, which showed: glucose levels at 7:00h - 8.0 mmol/L, at 12:00h - 6.35 mmol/L, at 18:00h - 5.3 mmol/L, at 22:00h - 5.6 mmol/L, and HbA1c at 7.5% (normal range below 5.7%). The ECG showed sinus rhythm, ventricular extrasystole. Dermatological examination revealed a disseminated polymorphic rash involving the face (Figure 1), trunk (Figure 2a, 2b, Figure 3), upper (Figure 4a) and lower (Figure 4b) limbs.

Figure 1: Diffuse Erythema on the Face, in a Sun-Exposed Area, Accompanied by Scaling. Actinic and Seborrhic Keratoses Can Be Observed on the Face and Neck Areas

Erythematous plaques of various sizes with fine desquamation were present. Annular lesions with a prominent, active erythematous edge and central clearing, often accompanied by peripheral scaling, were also observed (Figure 2a, 2b).

Figure 2a, 2b: Erythematous Plaques of Various Sizes with Fine Desquamation are Present. Annular Lesions with a Prominent, Active Erythematous Edge and Central Clearing, Often Accompanied by Peripheral Scaling, are also Observed. In Addition, Pigmented Maculopapular Plaques are Noted

Figure 3: A well-Demarcated Plaque, Measuring Approximately 10-12 cm in Diameter, Violaceous in Color, with a Hyperpigmented Center, Located in the Left Lower Back Region. Peripheral Hyperpigmented Edge with Silvery Scales and Crusting Erosions in Some Areas are Seen

In addition, pigmented maculopapular plaques were noted (Figure 2a, 2b; Figure 3; Figure 4). The inguinal and axillary regions showed altered skin morphology with cicatricial changes, but without evidence of active nodules or draining fistulas. Onychomycosis was also

clinically evident. Enlarged lymph nodes were not palpable.

Figure 4a, 4b: Well-Demarcated Violaceous to Erythematous Patches and Plaques with Scaling and Hyperpigmentation are Seen in the Left Upper (a) and Lower Leg (b) Regions

Regarding the polymorphic rash distributed across the entire body and accompanied by mild pruritus, several conditions were considered in the differential diagnostic plan, including the possibility of an overlap syndrome. The main differential diagnoses included erythema necroliticum migrans, parapsoriasis, erythema annulare, and mycosis fungoides. Four skin biopsies were obtained from different lesions.

Figure 5: ENM x 100 x HE Parakeratosis, Abundant Apoptotic Cells, Psoriasiform Hyperplasia, and Prominant Angioplasia in the Papillary Dermis

The biopsy taken from the abdominal area revealed parakeratosis, patchy acanthosis, single apoptotic keratinocytes and serum vesicles forming superficial necrosis, moderate lymphocytic exocytosis diffusely obscuring the dermo-epidermal junction, moderate perivascular and interstitial round cell inflammatory infiltrate in the upper and middle dermal compartments. The histological picture was consistent with erythema necrolyticum migrans (Figure 5; Figure 6; Figure 7).

Figure 6: ENM x 200 x HE Apoptotic Cells in the Superficial Epidermal Segment

Figure 7: ENM x 200 x HE Neutrophil Exocytosis and Papillary Dermis Angioplasia

The biopsy taken from the sacral region revealed orthohyperkeratosis, absence of the granular layer, uniform acanthosis with elongation and club-shaped dilatation of the distal portions of the epidermal ridges, focal perivascular round cell inflammatory infiltrate in the papillary dermis, and dilated small-caliber vessels in the upper dermal compartment. The histological constellation is consistent with erythema necrolyticum migrans with a prevailing psoriasiform component, likely in the clinical context of a resolving drug-induced, viral, or paraneoplastic exanthem.

The biopsy taken from the lumbar region revealed orthohyperkeratosis alternating horizontally with parakeratotic crusts, uniform acanthosis, moderate spongiosis, lymphocytic exocytosis, and occasional apoptotic bodies in the superficial layers of the epidermis. A moderate perivascular round cell inflammatory infiltrate was observed in the upper dermis. The histological picture was consistent with erythema necrolyticum migrans with a prevailing subacute psoriasiform component. This finding can correspond to the convalescent phase of a drug-induced and/or viral exanthem.

The biopsy taken from the right cubital region revealed parakeratosis, uniform acanthosis, lymphocytic exocytosis, and moderate spongiosis in the superficial segment of the epidermis. Additionally, a sparse to moderate perivascular round cell inflammatory infiltrate was noted in the papillary dermis. The histological constellation was consistent with erythema necrolyticum migrans with a prevailing psoriasiform component.

Treatment was initiated with levocetirizine dihydrochloride 5 mg once daily, and topical chloropyramine hydrochloride gel applied twice daily for two days. This was subsequently replaced with clobetasol propionate cream applied twice daily, along with a hydrating gel cream. Additionally, a contrast-enhanced CT scan of the chest, abdomen, and pelvis was performed to investigate a possible paraneoplastic origin of the skin rash. The imaging revealed limited pneumofibrotic changes, hepatic steatosis, a cyst in the left kidney, and sigmoid colon diverticulosis.

After receiving the biopsy results and considering a possible drug-induced etiology of the condition, consultations were conducted with both a cardiologist and an endocrinologist to revise the patient's medications. The revised regimen included acetylsalicylic acid 100 mg once in the evening, rosuvastatin/ezetimibe 10mg/10mg once daily in the evening, ivabradine 7.5mg twice daily, spironolactone 25 mg once in the morning, torasemide 10 mg once daily in the morning, rilmenidine 1mg twice daily, doxazosin 2 mg half a tablet twice daily (to be increased to one tablet twice daily if blood pressure exceeds

130/80), semaglutide 14 mg once daily in the morning, and metformin hydrochloride 850 mg twice daily. Methylprednisolone 10 mg intravenously once daily and famotidine 40 mg once daily were added to the systemic therapy. Upon discharge, the patient was recommended to continue systemic therapy with methylprednisolone 4 mg orally, following a tapering schedule: 1-1-0 for 5 days; then 1-1/2-0 for 5 days, followed by 1/2-1/2-0 for 5 days; and finally 1/2-0-0 for 5 days. Additional medications included esomeprazole 20 mg twice daily for 20 days, desloratadine 5 mg once daily for 20 days, clotrimazole cream 10mg/g applied 2-3 times daily for 20 days and methylprednisolone aceponate 0.1% cream applied once daily for 20 days. In order to exclude a potential paraneoplastic etiology, gastroscopy and colonoscopy, along with laboratory testing for serum glucagon, free fatty acids, zinc levels, and amino acid levels were recommended. The result of the radioimmunoassay glucagon was 146 ng/L (normal range <209 ng/L). The zinc levels were within the normal range, on the decreased side: 12.65 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ (normal range 12.0-24.0 $\mu\text{mol/l}$). The free fatty acids were slightly abnormal: low levels of Alpha-linolenic acid (ALA) - 7,72 mg/l (8,8 - 40 mg/l), low levels of eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) - 6,22 mg/l (16,41 - 56,54 mg/l), low Omega-3 index - 3,5 (Ratio > 8), high Omega-6/Omega-3 ratio - 10,6 (Ratio < 8), low EPA/AA ratio (eicosanoid balance) - 1,5 (Ratio > 15), and high Arachidonic acid levels of 405,36 mg/l (230 - 377 mg/l). Amino acid status was also recommended but the patient denied due to personal reasons.

Discussion

Necrolytic migratory erythema is regarded by some authors as one of the five well-defined cutaneous paraneoplastic syndromes, typically arising in the context of pancreatic A-cell glucagonoma [3].

The pathogenesis of necrolytic migratory erythema remains unclear; elevated serum glucagon levels are unlikely to be sole [4] - or even the primary - mechanism, as evidenced in our case.

Although rare, there are documented cases of necrolytic migratory erythema with characteristic clinical and histological findings occurring without any evidence of underlying neoplasia [3], [5]. Such a case is similar to the one presented by Tanner et al [3], in which the patient exhibited NME in the absence of glucagonoma. A possible connection to chronic persistent hepatitis, hepatocellular dysfunction and hypoalbuminemia was suggested as the cause of the skin changes [3,6,7].

A case report by Kasper et al [8] described a patient with necrolytic migratory erythema in the absence of glucagonoma, who also had diabetes mellitus and hepatic failure. In this report hyperglucagonemia was considered unlikely to be a main contributing factor, further supporting the hypothesis that different

etiological mechanisms - such as hepatic dysfunction - may play a pivotal role in the pathogenesis of NME [8]. In line with these findings, a similar constellation is observed in our patient, who has a medical history of hepatic steatosis and type 2 diabetes mellitus. Although still a hypothesis, our findings contribute to the growing evidence suggesting that liver impairment - either alone or in association with type 2 diabetes mellitus [9] - may be a key factor in the development of NME in cases of pseudoglucagonoma.

Necrolytic migratory erythema has also been reported as a rare drug-induced adverse event following prolonged subcutaneous dasiglucagon administration, a synthetic glucagon analog used in the treatment of congenital hyperinsulinism [10]. Discontinuation of the drug led to marked improvement in the patient's skin and nutritional status [10], suggesting a possible drug-induced mechanism of NME pathogenesis. A similar pattern was observed in our case: after discontinuation and replacement of certain antidiabetic and antihypertensive medications, the patient's condition began to gradually improve, further supporting the hypothesis of a multifactorial etiology of NME.

Malnutrition appears to play a substantial role in the pathogenesis of pseudoglucagonoma syndrome [11]. The role of dietary essential fatty acids, amino acids and zinc deficiency has been implied in several pseudoglucagonoma cases [12-15]. Obesity alone is a risk factor for zinc deficiency, especially after surgical interventions [16]. This supports the concept of a "chain reaction" involving multiple associated factors leading to the development of pseudoglucagonoma syndrome.

Oral supplementation with zinc has been shown to result in rapid and complete resolution of the eruption [17]. Additional management with intravenous amino acid and lipid infusions, has also demonstrated good results [18].

The closest comparable case (to our case) involved a necrolytic migratory erythema-like eruption alongside paradoxical psoriasis, reportedly linked to adalimumab treatment [19].

A potential association with underlying small-bowel disorders has been discussed in two reported cases of NME occurring without elevated glucagon levels or evidence of a pancreatic islet cell tumor [20]. Accordingly, gastro- and colonoscopy were recommended to our patient to investigate possible involvement of the gastrointestinal tract.

Interestingly, an idiopathic case of NME has also been described [21]. In the mentioned article, no glucagonoma or underlying disease could be identified [21]. Treatment with oral dapsone led to an excellent response, making it a possible therapeutic approach [22].

The necrolytic migratory erythema lesion was most likely/ probably triggered by the patient's pharmacological treatment for type 2 diabetes mellitus and arterial hypertension. This conclusion is supported by the visual improvement of the lesions after discontinuation and replacement of certain medications suspected to exacerbate the condition. Although the specific drug responsible for the reaction remains unidentified, a drug-induced etiology appears highly possible. The presence of hepatic steatosis, and/or disbalance in the fatty acid levels, may further contribute to or exacerbate the dermatological manifestations.

Conclusions

Based on the case presented, we propose an updated classification of necrolytic migratory erythema based on different clinical presentations and underlying non-neoplastic pathogenetic mechanisms. The following classification may serve as a practical framework for diagnostic evaluation of NME and more personalized therapeutic approach: 1) Nutritional/Zinc deficiency-related NME, 2) Drug-induced NME, 3) Metabolically associated NME (diabetes mellitus, hepatic impairment, and etc), and 4) Idiopathic NME. A multifactorial genesis of necrolytic migratory erythema may be proposed in the context of polymedication.

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